

microRNA-21/PDCD4 Proapoptotic Signaling From Circulating CD34+ Cells to Vascular Endothelial Cells: A Potential Contributor to Adverse Cardiovascular Outcomes in Patients With Critical Limb Ischemia

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Understanding the molecular basis of cardiovascular complications of diabetes mellitus

What is it about?

Limb ischemia is a serious problem for people with type 2 diabetes leading to increased risk of amputation and death for cardiovascular causes. We here show for the first time that the endogenous systems deputed to vascular repair and blood flow restoration are altered by the diabetic environment. In particular, circulating proangiogenic cells of diabetic patients are transformed into negative players vehiculating molecular signals of death to the vessels.

Why is it important?

Assessing the molecular markers identified in this study may help identify high-risk patients for whom more aggressive treatments are necessary. In addition, the new signaling pathways associated with the disease severity may be valuable targets for future therapies.

Perspectives

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I enjoyed writing this article since it was a great opportunity to exchange ideas between basic scientists and clinicians in a truly translational research effort.

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